

Project:
NANOFACTS
Grant Agreement (GA) No. 952259

**“NETWORKING ACTIVITIES FOR NANOTECHNOLOGY-FACILITATED CANCER
THERANOSTICS”**

Call: H2020-WIDESPREAD-2020-5

Topic: WIDESPREAD-05-2020 - Twinning

Type of action: CSA - Coordination and support action

**D6.7: Evolution of the Publications in High Impact Journals in the
Relevant Research Fields**

Start date of project: 01/01/2021

Duration: 36 months

Document History
(Revisions – Amendments)

Version and date	Changes
1.1. 15/02/2021	Nikola Knežević (PC)
1.2. 25/02/2021	Nikola Knežević (PC)

Dissemination Level

PU	Public	X
PP	Restricted to other programme participants (including the EC Services)	
RE	Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the EC Services)	
CO	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the EC)	

Continuous reporting tool which measures the evolution (compared to a reference period of three years prior to the signature of the grant agreement) in % of the peer-reviewed publications in high impact journals (in the top 10% impact ranked journals) in the research area related to nanomaterials for cancer therapy and diagnostics.

Total of 3 articles have been published at the Biosense institute in the research area related to nanomaterials for cancer therapy and diagnostics in the period of three years prior to the signature of the grant agreement. The list of publications has been entered on the Funding and tenders portal as follows:

1. Chaix A, Cueto-Diaz E, Delalande A, Knezevic N, Midoux P, Durand J-O, et al. Amino-acid functionalized porous silicon nanoparticles for the delivery of pDNA. RSC Adv. 2019; 9(55):31895–9.: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1039/C9RA05461H7>; IF 2019 = 3.119; Rank: Chemistry, Multidisciplinary (73/177)
2. Knežević NŽ, Gadjanski I, Durand J-O. Magnetic nanoarchitectures for cancer sensing, imaging and therapy. J Mater Chem B. 2019; 7(1):9–23. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1039/C8TB02741B>; IF 2019 = 5.344; Rank: Materials Science, Biomaterials (9/38)
3. Knežević NŽ, Djordjević S, Kojić V, Janačković D. Functionalized periodic mesoporous organosilica nanoparticles for loading and delivery of suramin. Inorganics. 2019; 7(2). <https://doi.org/10.3390/inorganics7020016>; IF 2019 = N/A; Rank: N/A

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